

Innovative artificial intelligence strategies for enhancing nutritional interventions in aging people

Raul Alonso-Calvo¹, Sonia de Pascual-Teresa², Miguel García-Remesal¹

¹Biomedical Informatics Group, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Boadilla del Monte, Spain

²Spanish National Research Council | CSIC · Institute of Food Science and Technology and Nutrition (ICTAN), Madrid, Spain

Background and aims: The KEPHENOL project aims to explore the benefits of polyphenols consumption in mitigating cardiovascular and cognitive decline associated with aging. We have crafted a comprehensive dietary intervention centered on the consumption of 93 key foods, selected from Food Frequency Questionnaires (FFQ) given to the 150 volunteers during the first visit of the study. To accurately assess the participants' dietary intake, access to various Food Composition Databases (FCDB) is essential. Bringing together heterogeneous required information is challenging, demanding substantial time and effort from researchers.

Methods: Our proposed methodology integrates different Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques for creating a machine learning model. The latter employs syntactic analysis of food labels, bolstered by a fuzzy search mechanism leveraging dictionaries. Furthermore, we explored Deep Learning (DL) models to improve the accuracy of the task. These different approaches were integrated to create a comprehensive pipeline for matching food labels among the selected FCDBs.

Results: Resorting to fuzzy string matching alongside syntactic analysis yielded promising results for raw products. Additionally, leveraging DL sentence embeddings allowed us to recommend related foods by enhancing the original text with semantic similarity. The 93 foods chosen underwent processing to obtain their corresponding codes in FoodEx2, BEDCA, and PhenolExplorer2 databases. Obtained codes were evaluated and manually revised to validate the final codes.

Conclusion: We present a novel methodology that employs semantic text similarity for automating code selection within FoodEx2, BEDCA and PhenolExplorer2. Results suggest that integrating innovative AI methods into the field of nutritional intervention can streamline researchers' daily tasks.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, Natural Language Processing, Food Composition Database integration, BEDCA, PhenolExplorer2, FoodEx2.

Innovative Artificial Intelligence strategies for enhancing nutritional interventions in aging people

Raul Alonso-Calvo¹, Sonia de Pascual-Teresa², Miguel García-Remesal¹

¹Biomedical Informatics Group, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Boadilla del Monte, Spain

²Spanish National Research Council | CSIC · Institute of Food Science and Technology and Nutrition (ICTAN), Madrid, Spain

Objectives:

- The **KEPHENOL** project investigates **the benefits of polyphenol consumption in mitigating age-related cardiovascular and cognitive decline** through a comprehensive nutritional intervention focused on the intake of **93 key foods** selected from our FFQ.
- To accurately assess participants' dietary intake, access to multiple food composition databases (FCDBs) is essential.
- **Collecting the required heterogeneous information** is a challenge that demands substantial time and effort from researchers.

Materials and Methods:

- We used different **artificial intelligence (AI) techniques** (sentence and word embeddings) and **machine learning (ML)** methods (TF-IDF, lemmatization, and tokenization) to analyze food labels.
- A comprehensive workflow was developed to match food labels across the selected FCDBs.

Results and discussion:

- **Promising results** were obtained for the automatic linkage between terminologies.
- For simple foods (PhenolExplorer2), the results are very good, and for composite foods (meals with multiple ingredients), AI enables the recommendation of potentially related foods by enhancing the original text through semantic similarity.
- The 93 foods selected for the study were processed (BEDCA and PhenolExplorer2) to obtain their corresponding FoodEx2 codes.
- The resulting codes were evaluated and **manually reviewed to validate the final codes**.

Conclusions:

- We present a novel methodology that uses semantic text **similarity to automate the selection of FoodEx2 codes for BEDCA and PhenolExplorer**.

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

